

How Researchers can convert their Thesis or Dissertations to Journal Articles for Publications

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BACKGROUND

A thesis or dissertation is a document of academic nature, and so it is more detailed in content. A journal article, however, is a shorter academic write-up that highlight key points in a more succinct design [1]. Converting a thesis or dissertation into a journal article or manuscript is a logical process and involves certain useful steps [1, 2]. Depending on the experience of the researchers, such process can be time-consuming and may be complex and intricate. In others, it may be an easy and enjoyable process. The authors or researchers may embark on the conversion process with or without professional help. The researchers are encouraged not to delay the process immediately after their successful thesis or dissertation defense. Some institutions also require that such conversion be done before the final defense since publication of some component of the dissertation is needed for successful defense. Good knowledge of such steps or recruitment of professional help may help fast-track the conversion and publication process.

PROCESSES AND STEPS OF CONVERTING THE DISSERTATION OR THESIS TO JOURNAL ARTICLE

The following process and steps are needed for conversion of the thesis or dissertations to journal article.

Journal

First and foremost, the researchers should decide the potential journal for submission of the manuscript. This should be decided before conversion from the Dissertation to journal article. However, the choice of journal can be decided any time in the conversion process. The researchers should Google to find the instruction for authors in their chosen journal. To decide on the journal, the authors should consider the quality of their work and quality of the journal they wish to send their papers to. As usual, the researchers should aim high initially to submit their manuscript in journals that are indexed in SCOPUS or PUBMED or at least Google scholar. To easily decide on a journal with high impact, the researchers can search the acronym JANE (Journal/Author Name Estimator) available at

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Specialty Section:

This article was submitted to
Editorial, a section of TJMR.

Received: 15 October 2022

Accepted: xx

Published: 9 November 2022

Citation:

George Uchenna Eleje, Lydia
Ijeoma Eleje, Chigozie Geoffrey
Okafor: How Researchers can
convert their Thesis or
Dissertations to Journal
Articles for journal
publications. Trop J Med Res.
2022;21(2);xix-xxii.
DOI:10.5281/zenodo.7774042.

Access Code

<http://tjmr.org.ng>

<https://jane.biosemantics.org>. JANE is a free online tool that can be used to find articles that are similar to the abstract, title, or keywords input into it [3]. JANE's indexing criteria include journals from PubMed/MEDLINE that contain abstracts published within the past ten years [3].

Title

The title should be brief, catchy and interesting for global readership. Depending on some journal, the name of the institution, city or country where the work was conducted may not be included in the title. Such may be carefully done to avoid biasing international readership.

Short Title

Here the researchers should include a short title that should not be more than 50 characters.

Authors

Here the researchers will include the names of those that contributed substantially to the work, to merit inclusion.

Affiliations

In affiliations, the researches should include the institutional affiliations of the potential authors.

Correspondence

Here, one of the researcher will show the foremost responsibility for the day to day running of the article submission. The corresponding authors will also be responsible for monitoring reviewing and editorial processes and ensure timely response.

Abstract

In abstract, the researchers should ensure that the abstract is structured, complies with the journal requirements and conveys the key points of the study. However, some journals may not require structured abstract. The knowledge of each journal's instructions for authors is the key. The researchers should be strict with the journal's word-count requirements.

Key Words

Here, the authors will state 4 to 6 key words arranged alphabetically and separated by semicolon.

INTRODUCTION

In introduction, the authors may wish to combine the background information of the dissertation or thesis as well as the justification and or statement of the problem as Introduction.

The introduction section should be improved according to the literature gap. It should not be long. In introduction, the researchers should shorten the introduction of the thesis or dissertation so that it does not exceed four or five paragraphs, but they should maintain key information to hold the reader's attention [1]. In introduction, the authors should focus on what is known, what remains unclear, knowledge gap they seek to fill, identify a research question and justify the need for the study [2].

METHODS

In the method section, the language and grammar should be re-checked and corrected. It should be ensured that it remains in the past tense. Ethical approval institution, ethical approval number and date should be added especially in health research. Tests used for either normally or non-normally distributed continuous variables should be described in the statistical analysis part.

If the researcher did a randomized control trial, the authors need to state in the Methods section of their manuscript that they have followed CONSORT: 'The reporting of this study conforms to the CONSORT statements.

The authors should indicate how the sample size was calculated. The researchers should ensure that they include a sample size calculation. If so, include the result in the Statistics section of the manuscript and state the result – i.e. number of patients needed in your study to show significance. If you did not perform a sample size calculation, you need to state that they did not perform a sample size calculation.

If the researchers have not registered your clinical

trial: To prevent non-publication of research involving human participants, some journals consider retrospectively registered studies. If so, the author should immediately register his trial at the Research Registry and state the following in his Methods section: 'In error, we did not prospectively register this trial, but we have now registered it retrospectively at the Research Registry <https://www.researchregistry.com/>. registration number xxx.' Also, state it at the end of the Abstract state: 'Research Registry number: xxx.'

If the authors are working on risk factors, the authors should have performed univariate logistic regression analysis to select factors for multivariate logistic regression analysis. The authors should ensure that continuous variables with normal distribution are presented as mean \pm standard deviation (SD) whereas those without normal distribution are presented as median and interquartile range (IQR). Quantitative data should be analyzed using the χ^2 or Fisher exact test. The authors should ensure that continuous variables are compared between groups using *t*-test or Mann–Whitney non-parametric test, as appropriate. For more than 2 comparison group, the authors may state that the comparisons between three study groups were performed using one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) test. They may state that A *P*-value < 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Results

The researchers should provide information regarding the findings of their research in concise format. This section should be free from discussion and should be written in past tense.

Discussion

In this section, the authors are expected to compare their results with previous papers, and also cite those papers [2]. Discussion involves providing an interpretation of the researchers' results [2]. They should discuss the relevance and novelty of their study and what it adds to the literature. The authors

should mention related studies to provide readers with appropriate interpretations. The authors should pay attention to mentioning more related studies with respect to their study [2].

The authors should also mention the practical implication, strengths and limitations of the study, before finally appending the conclusion of their manuscript.

Conclusion

The researchers should conclude based on their findings and addresses relevant implications for practice or policy.

References

The researchers should ensure that the references are not more than 35 in cases of original articles. Additionally, depending on the time the thesis or the dissertation was defended, the references may need to be updated if more than 5 or 10 years have elapsed from the time of final defense. The researchers should ensure that the majority of their references are within 10 years.

Figure Legends

The researchers should state the title of the figures and figure numbers included the manuscript. One of the figures should be a flow diagram. The choice of the flow chart or flow diagram depends on the type of study design.

Table Legends

The researchers should state the title of the tables and table numbers included the manuscript.

Tables Attached

In some journals, Tables and figures are attached separately or can be merged as one manuscript but listed at the end of the manuscript. The researchers should simply follow the instructions for authors in their relevant submission. In this table space, the researchers should attach all the necessary tables. The tables should not be more than 5 or 7 tables. In some journals, the tables should not be more than 4.

You can merge tables to reduce the number. In some cases, the thesis or dissertation should be split into two or more journal articles depending on the outcomes and data studied. However, in cases where articles are split, efforts should be made to publish the original primary article first while others may serve as secondary analysis. Tables should not include duplicate data that has been explained in the text

Figures Attached

In this section, the researchers should attach all the necessary figures including the flow chart of the participants in the study.

Substracter

The researcher (s) should remove other headings like literature review, statement of problem, justification of study, etc. remove bar chart and pie chart. The authors should include only tables, figures and flow diagram (if possible). However, they should have their final decision to either to include bar chart or pie chart or not.

Addendum

Depending on the journal the authors wish to submit their work, the authors should ensure that the following sections are written at the end of their manuscript: Author contributions, Declaration of conflicting interests, Funding, Acknowledgements, Data availability statement and Ethical approval statement.

Language Editing Services

When the journal articles are finally prepared, the researchers should employ a language editing services or can use a free online grammar check such as *Grammarly*. Millions trust *Grammarly's* free writing app that make their online manuscript writing clear and effective.

CONCLUSION

Publishing a journal article from a thesis or dissertation is a worthwhile endeavor. This involves identifying the best journal for the manuscript,

reformatting the abstract, modifying the introduction, tightening the method section, reporting the main findings in the work, ensuring that the discussion is concise and clear and limiting the number of references.

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